

THE MANIFESTATION OF INFANTILISM IN PARENT-CHILD RELATIONSHIPS

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Annotation: Parental infantilism is a very rare, atypical and still poorly studied phenomenon for modern society, and is presented as a complex systemic formation. The article discusses the socio-psychological factors of the emergence of infantilism in the institution of modern parenting based on the analysis of materials from scientific publications that study the psychological characteristics of infantile parents and their psychological problems.

Key words: interpersonal relationships, psychological dysfunction, demographic factors, socialization, psychological investment.

In the era of transformation of values and traditions taking place in the world, one of the main tasks that modern science should solve is to study the role of the family in children's behavioral deviations. It is in the family that the foundation of the child's social experience, value system, character and intelligence is laid, and individual psychological characteristics are formed, on the basis of which a model of interaction between the individual and the outside world is formed. At a time when socio-economic changes are accelerating, changes in family structures, the composition and structure of the family and family life, lifestyle, forms of social control and participation, as well as the impact of fundamentally new social norms of behavior on the educational process have become widespread. These aspects create the basis for the sustainable development of such negative aspects as indifference and irresponsibility of parents in the system of family relations. In the next analysis, we can see that, having studied the socio-psychological factors that cause aggression in adolescents, the relationship between the adolescent's parents, as well as the relationship between the parents and their adolescent child, can also have an impact, as confirmed by the results of our research [1].

The methodological basis of the psychology of family relations is the theory of freedom, equality and dignity. The ideology of the psychology of family relations is the well-being of the family, the strengthening and development of the family way of life, equal opportunities for personal development, the priority of the interests of the child. Theoretical and practical interest in the problem of

the family exists as long as human society exists, and this is not surprising. The family is a system of human social activity, one of the main institutions of society. It is in motion, changing not only under the influence of socio-political conditions, but also due to the internal processes of its development [2]. The family is the object of research of many social sciences, such as philosophy, history, ethnography, sociology, demography, psychology of family relations. Each of these sciences seeks to give its own definition of the family and therefore develops its own approaches to the study of this problem. According to A.I. Antonov, the family is “an association of people based on personal property and family activity, connected with parental-marriage-kinship relations, which combine the satisfaction of personal needs and the performance of social functions by birth, an institution for the maintenance and socialization of children”. Psychology, studying the family as a socio-psychological group, pays attention to the interpersonal relationships of its members, their interaction in various social and family situations, the organization of family life and the factors of the stability of the family as a small group. At the same time, the family is interpreted as a social group united by a set of interpersonal relationships formed in joint activities, corresponding to the norms and values of a particular society [5].

Infantilism among parents began to develop rapidly in the 20th century, especially in its second half. This was undoubtedly influenced by technical progress, the transformation of the family institution, family values, and the socio-psychological role of men and women in family relations. The interpretation of the concept of “infantilism” and the study of its manifestation in parental behavior seem to the authors to be a pressing issue characterizing one of the modern trends in development. In everyday practice, this term is often used as an assessment of a particular phenomenon or behavior and has a negative connotation [3]. Such a negative assessment is appropriate for the world of parents. Every child is “immature” and strives to become a full-fledged adult. Despite the possible problems and difficulties of adult life, the position of adults seems attractive to the child. Indeed, achieving maturity and elevation is one of the promising goals of human development. Profound changes taking place in many areas of life lead to a change in the value-semantic relations of parents, to the setting of goals that are easier and faster to achieve. The modern social situation is characterized by an increase in the volume and intensity of information flows, socio-economic changes and various crises. The contradictory picture of the future, the uncertainty of tomorrow scares future parents, as if

calling them to remain in “childhood”, where there were no problems, life was stable and reliable. However, having lost the value of growing up, humanity loses the meaning of its existence, denies self-reproduction and is heading towards a decrease in the population and the end of humanity. In the analysis of the questionnaire «Parent-child relationship» by A.Ya. Varga and V.V. Stolin, 90 parents of our adolescent subjects who participated in our study participated, and they were analyzed based on the class section. Accordingly, we can see that there was no significant difference between the results of parents of adolescent students on the acceptance scale ($H=1.569$, $p \geq 0.456$). The average rank index of parents of 5th grade students is 40.90, the average rank index of parents of 7th grade students is 46.43, and the average rank index of parents of 9th grade students is 49.17. Furthermore, the acceptance of adolescent children by parents of 9th grade students is lower than that of parents of other grades. This is because parents believe that since their children are on the verge of «stepping into independent life,» they use a method of satisfying their behavior, desires, and needs with an eye on their future field of activity in order to prevent them from straying into various strange paths.

Traditionally, the development of the individual is influenced by three global factors: heredity, environment and upbringing. Numerous scientific experiments conducted by nature on humans prove that the child is able to perfectly adapt to the animal environment, but the further it is, the faster it loses its ability to develop personally. Consequently, it is the environment that is the leading factor influencing the properties and qualities of future generations. The transmitter of the environment, everything that is nature, all the blessings created by people, is culture in a broad sense [7].

In the course of the above theoretical analysis, we can divide the pedagogical conditions for the development of infantilism in parents into the following categories:

- 1) the lack of collective education and the low influence of teachers, psychologists and the educational environment in general on the development of the individual;
- 2) a specific style of freedom pedagogy, which provokes the development of egoism;
- 3) in the absence of psychological and pedagogical support for family relationships, the responsibility for upbringing is assigned only to the family;
- 3) deformation of the model of family relations against the background of a decrease in the birth rate, changes in gender roles and family values.

An alarming symptom of infantilism is the lack of desire to develop. Analyzing the work of Dan Keeley and many other researchers, it becomes clear that there are six main signs of infantilism in parents:

- 1) irresponsible behavior;
- 2) psychological discomfort;
- 3) loneliness and hidden fears;
- 4) confusion of gender roles;
- 5) narcissism;
- 6) gender stereotypes [6].

The loss of the value of adulthood undermines the development goals of humanity and the stability of the population. For a modern young person, the main components of youth remain stable at the level of adolescence. The leading activity is the same as in adolescence - mastering the operational-technical side, professional orientation and acquiring professional skills. Another prerequisite for the implementation of development is communication, which has become mediated directly through digital and virtual devices - computers, mobile devices, social networks, file-sharing services. Mediated social interaction leads to the equalization of the importance of certain behavioral patterns and gaps in their formation. There is a tendency to replace real communication with virtual. All other things being equal, modern youth prefer signs of attention (for example, congratulations on a birthday or other significant event) on social networks to direct communication. Virtual communication is characterized by superficial connections and imitation of emotions. As a result, this leads to a violation of the influence of the social factor on development and maturation. Infantilism remains a “natural” model of behavior, supported by the components of development for both a young person and a biological adult [8].

To form stable psychological boundaries, responsibility and activity of the individual, there must be an effective communication system between the individual, family and society. For the effective functioning of the education system as the main channel for the transmission of cultural meanings, dialogical interaction between family education, the state education system and the real socio-cultural context of state education of the younger generation should be ensured. Based on theoretical analyses, the study of the manifestation of infantilism in parents reveals the possibility of psychocorrection and psychoprophylaxis of infantilism by focusing on their family path, marital hierarchy, and the “psychological wounds” they received when passing a certain age stage in ontogenesis. As modern preventive measures to prevent the

development of infantilism among young people on the verge of marriage, that is, future parents, it is worth noting the following:

1) the formation of a pedagogical and social environment that stimulates the development of social activity and social intelligence of young people;

2) the restoration of collective and labor education methods that form personal development, independence, and enhance the influence of a peer group in the educational process;

3) the provision of educational and psychological and pedagogical support of society to families (especially single-parent families) in diagnosing and preventing infantilism in the practice of family upbringing;

4) create conditions for real self-realization here and now, in order to prevent young people from entering mythological worlds (the world of virtual games, digital reconstructions of communication, drugs, illusions, artificially created subcultures);

5) develop young people's aspirations for independence (including financial independence), first of all, self-confidence, their capabilities and abilities;

6) support at the state and societal levels the culture of family relations, large families, the decisive role and responsibility of the father as a regulator of family relations and the rules of upbringing;

7) develop and introduce into the educational process methods of combating digital safety and Internet addiction for the development of a creative personality;

8) development of educational programs on self-knowledge, self-development, self-management and self-education technologies in the youth environment and their introduction into the educational process;

9) implementation of preventive work aimed at combating the growing tendency of teachers and psychologists in youth communities to blame parents and seek "childhood injuries" to explain the manifestation of their own infantile behavior.

10) development and implementation of programs and projects to increase the social activity of young people in order to develop the younger generation in harmony with nature and society, to form a sense of responsibility and creative self-awareness of a modern person [7].

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